

Table 2S Supplementary. Immunodominant epitopes for adult groups (comparison between groups pediatric/mild/severe). Amino acids marked in red indicate overlapped sequences.

Peptide	Organism	Protein	Sequence	p-value	Comparison groups	AUC
NCAP_SARS2_0157-0171	SARS-CoV-2	N	IVLQLPQGTTLPKGF	9.9X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.773
NCAP_SARS2_0161-0175	SARS-CoV-2	N	LPQGTTLPKGFYAEG	4.9X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.796
NCAP_SARS2_0221-0235	SARS-CoV-2	N	LLLLDLRLNQLQESKMS	1.6X10 ⁻⁵	Mild/Sev	0.924
NCAP_SARS2_0393-0407	SARS-CoV-2	N	TLLPAADLDDFSKQL	1X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.84
SPIKE_SARS2_0557-0571	SARS-CoV-2	S	KKFLPFQQFGRDIAD	8.6X10 ⁻³	MILD/SEV	0.778
SPIKE_SARS2_0785-0799	SARS-CoV-2	S	VKQIYKTPPIKDFGG	1X10 ⁻⁴	Mild/Sev	0.889
SPIKE_SARS2_0789-0803	SARS-CoV-2	S	YKTPPIKDFGGFNFS	2X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.822
SPIKE_SARS2_1145-1159	SARS-CoV-2	S	LDSFKEELDKYFKNH	1.2X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.836
R1A_R1AB_SARS2_0249-0263	SARS-CoV-2	NsP	YELQTPFEIKLAKKF	4.8X10 ⁻³	Asym/mild	0.926
R1AB_SARS2_6073-6087	SARS-CoV-2	NsP	HLIPLMYKGLPWNVV	5.7X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.791
NCAP_CVHSA_0157-0171	SARS-CoV	N	ATVLQLPQGTTLPKG	2.3X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.818
NCAP_CVHSA_0161-0175	SARS-CoV	N	QLPQGTTLPKGFYAE	6.6X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.787
NCAP_CVHSA_0221-0235	SARS-CoV	N	ALLLLDLRLNQLQESKV	6X10 ⁻⁴	Mild/Sev	0.786
NCAP_CVHSA_0393-0407	SARS-CoV	N	VTLPAADMDDFSRQ	6.6X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.787
SPIKE_CVHSA_0185-0199	SARS-CoV	S	FVFNKNDGFLYVYKG	4.8X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.926
SPIKE_CVHSA_0645-0659	SARS-CoV	S	SYECDIPIGAGICAS	7.5X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.782
SPIKE_CVHSA_1129-1143	SARS-CoV	S	SFKEELDKYFKNHTS	2X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.822
SPIKE_CVEMC_0109-0123	MERS	S	VKQFANGFVVRIGAA	8X10 ⁻⁴	Mild/Sev	no
SPIKE_CVEMC_1225-1239	MERS	S	NSTGIDFQDELDEFF	1.6X10 ⁻³	Asym/ Mild	0.963
SPIKE_CVEMC_1229-1243	MERS	S	IDFQDELDEFFKNVS	8X10 ⁻⁴	Asym/mild	0.981
				9.9X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.773
SPIKE_CVH22_1133-1147	229E	S	LLLCCSTGCCGFFS	2X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.822
SPIKE_CVHNL_0557-0571	NL63	S	LNNFQKFKTICFSTV	4.9X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.204
SPIKE_CVHOC_0757-0771	OC43	S	RGAITTYRFTNFEP	7X10 ⁻⁴	Mild/Sev	0.151
SPIKE_CVHN1_0759_0773	HKU1	S	RRSISASYRFTFEP	6X10 ⁻⁴	Mild/Sev	0.147
SPIKE_CVHN2_0757_0771	HKU1	S	GISSPYRFTFEPFN	6.6X10 ⁻³	Mild/Sev	0.213

Table 2S supplementary. Immunodominant epitopes for children group (comparison between groups pediatric/mild/severe)

Peptide	Organism	Protein	Sequence	p-value	Comparison Group	AUC
NCAP_CVEMC_0089-0103	MERS	N	NGIKQLAPRWYFYIT	2.7X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.18
NCAP_CVEMC_0093-0107	MERS	N	QLAPRWYFYITGTGP	1X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.1
NCAP_CVEMC_0321-0335	MERS	N	DHGPNVYFLRYSGAI	5.9X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2
				9X10 ⁻⁴	PED/SEVE	0.15
NCAP_CVEMC_0357-0371	MERS	N	AYKTFPKKEKKQKAP	3.2X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.8
SPIKE_CVEMC_0265-0279	MERS	S	LFSSRYVDLYGGNMF	3X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.13
SPIKE_CVEMC_0289-0303	MERS	S	TIKYYSIIPHSIRSI	6.8X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.21
SPIKE_CVEMC_0493-0507	MERS	S	KPLKYSYINKCSRFL	3X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.13
SPIKE_CVEMC_1133-1147	MERS	S	GLYFMHVGYYPSNHI	3.2X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.18
NCAP_CVH22_0053-0067	229E	N	KLIGYWNVQKRFRTR	1.9X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.17
				1.3X10 ⁻⁵	PED/SEVE	0.067
NCAP_CVH22_0057-0071	229E	N	YWNVQKRFRTRKGR	6X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.14
NCAP_CVH22_0189-0203	229E	N	ALKSLGFDKPKQEKDK	4.3X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.8
SPIKE_CVH22_0189-0203	229E	S	TVREFVISRTGHFYI	3.2X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.18
SPIKE_CVH22_0193-0207	229E	S	FVISRTGHFYINGYR	8X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.14
				5.1X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.2
SPIKE_CVH22_0197-0211	229E	S	RTGHFYINGYRYFTL	1.1X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.15
				7.9X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.2
SPIKE_CVH22_0201-0215	229E	S	FYINGYRYFTLGNVE	4.3X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.19
SPIKE_CVH22_0489-0503	229E	S	GTIYSITPCNPPDQL	1.3X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.838
SPIKE_CVH22_0989-1003	229E	S	YYRITSRIMFEPRIIP	1.1X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.15
				4.3X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.19
SPIKE_CVH22_1097-1111	229E	S	STLVDLKWLNRVETY	3.2X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.18
SPIKE_CVH22_1105-1119	229E	S	LNRVETYIKWPWWVW	3X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.12
SPIKE_CVH22_1133-1147	229E	S	LLLCCCSGCGGFFS	2X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.114
VME1_CVH22_0033-0047	229E	M	QFGHYKYSRLFYGLK	1.9X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.17
				9.1X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.2
VME1_CVH22_0101-0115	229E	M	LFRRARTFWAWNPEV	1X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.09
				5X10 ⁻⁴	PED/SEVE	0.1

NCAP_CVHNL_0077-0091	NL63	N	HFYYLGTGPHKDLKF	6.8X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.21
SPIKE_CVHNL_0101-0115	NL63	S	VTLKICKFSRNTTFD	5.9X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.205
SPIKE_CVHNL_0149-0163	NL63	S	VRLHLYNVTRTFYVP	2.3X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.176
SPIKE_CVHNL_0153-0167	NL63	S	LYNVTRTFYVPAAYK	5.1X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2
				5.9X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.205
SPIKE_CVHNL_0541-0555	NL63	S	WHIYLKSGTCPFSSFS	1X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.105
SPIKE_CVHNL_1285-1299	NL63	S	LLNRFENYIKWPWWV	1X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.11
VME1_CVHNL_0033-0047	NL63	M	LQYGHYKYSRLLYGL	3X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.12
				6.8X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.2
VME1_CVHNL_0193-0207	NL63	M	TGWAFYVRAKHGDFS	4.3X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.19
				3.2X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.18
NCAP_CVHOC_0113-0127	OC43	N	DGNQRQLLPRWYFYY	8X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.14
				5.9X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.2
NCAP_CVHOC_0121-0135	OC43	N	PRWYFYYLGTGPHAK	2.7X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.18
NCAP_CVHOC_0261-0275	OC43	N	EVROKILNKPRQKRS	2X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.12
SPIKE_CVHOC_0081-0095	OC43	S	KGSVLLSRLWFKPPF	5X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.138
SPIKE_CVHOC_0085-0099	OC43	S	LLSRLWFKPPFLSDF	1.8X10 ⁻⁵	PED/MILD	0.071
SPIKE_CVHOC_0089-0103	OC43	S	LWFKPPFLSDFINGI	1X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.095
SPIKE_CVHOC_0237-0251	OC43	S	LFNVYLGMAISHYV	8X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.148
SPIKE_CVHOC_0261-0275	OC43	S	TLEYVWTPLTSRQYL	2.7X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.181
SPIKE_CVHOC_0445-0459	OC43	S	SRFNPSTWNKRFGFI	1.3X10 ⁻⁵	PED/MILD	0.067
SPIKE_CVHOC_0561-0575	OC43	S	YCGGNSCTCRPQAFI	3X10 ⁻⁴	PED/SEVE	0.124
SPIKE_CVHOC_1285-1299	OC43	S	KDIGTYEYVVKWPWY	2.7X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.181
NCAP_CVHSA_0101-0115	SARS-CoV	N	KMKELSPRWYFYLG	5.9X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2
NCAP_CVHSA_0157-0171	SARS-CoV	N	ATVLQLPQGTTLPKG	6.8X10 ⁻³	PEDI/MILD	0.79
NCAP_CVHSA_0221-0235	SARS-CoV	N	ALLLLDRLNQLSKV	7.9X10 ⁻³	PEDI/SEVER	0.786
NCAP_CVHSA_0253-0267	SARS-CoV	N	AEASKKPRQKRTATK	5X10 ⁻⁴	PED/SEVE	0.13
SPIKE_CVHSA_0189-0203	SARS-CoV	S	NKDGFLYVYKGYQPI	2.7X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.181
SPIKE_CVHSA_0305-0319	SARS-CoV	S	FRVVPDGDVVRFPNI	1X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.1
SPIKE_CVHSA_0353-0367	SARS-CoV	S	SVLYNSTFFSTFKCY	7.9X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.214

SPIKE_CVHSA_0537-0551	SARS-CoV	S	VLT PSSKRFPQPFQ	1.2X10 ⁻⁶	PED/MILD	0.033
				2.7X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.181
SPIKE_CVHSA_0541-0555	SARS-CoV	S	SS KRFQPFQ GRDV	3.7X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.19
SPIKE_CVHSA_0833-0847	SARS-CoV	S	CA QKFNG LTVLP PLL	1.3X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.838
SPIKE_CVHSA_1065-1079	SARS-CoV	S	HE GKAYFP REGV FVF	3.2X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.186
SPIKE_CVHSA_1125-1139	SARS-CoV	S	PE LDSFKE ELDKY FK	1.3X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.838
SPIKE_CVHSA_1129-1143	SARS-CoV	S	S FKEEL DKY FNH TS	2.7X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.819
VEMP_CVHSA_0061-0075	SARS-CoV	E	RV KNLNS SE GP DLL	5.1X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.8
NCAP_SARS2_0109-0123	SARS-CoV-2	N	Y FYYL GT GP EAG LPY	9.1X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2
NCAP_SARS2_0221-0235	SARS-CoV-2	N	L LLDRL N QLES KMS	8X10⁻⁴	PED/SEVE	0.852
NCAP_SARS2_0393-0404	SARS-CoV-2	N	T LLPAAD L DDFS Q L	1.9X10⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.829
NS7A_SARS2_0009-0023	SARS-CoV-2	NS7A	L ITLAT C ELYH Y QEC	3.2X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.18
NS8_SARS2_0033-0047	SARS-CoV-2	NS8A	V DDECP I HFY SK WYI	5.9X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2
R1A_R1AB_SARS2_2001-2015	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	A TYKNT W CIR CL WS	3X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.12
R1A_R1AB_SARS2_2157-2171	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	V TRCLN R VCTN Y MPY	1.3X10 ⁻⁵	PED/MILD	0.07
				4.3X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.2
R1A_R1AB_SARS2_3005-3019	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	V LNNDY Y RS L PGV F FC	5X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.13
R1A_R1AB_SARS2_3469-3483	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	A WLYAA V INGD R WFL	5.1X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2
R1A_R1AB_SARS2_4269-4283	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	F CAFAV D AAKAY K DY	3.7X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.19
R1AB_SARS2_4541-4555	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	Y NCCDD D YFN K KDWY	9.1X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2
R1AB_SARS2_4653-4667	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	L TKPYI K WDL L KYD F	1X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.1
R1AB_SARS2_4673-4687	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	K LFDRY F KYWD Q TYH	1.6X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.16
R1AB_SARS2_4725-4739	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	I FVDG V PVV ST GYH	6.8X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2
R1AB_SARS2_4729-4743	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	G VFPV V STGY H FREL	7.9X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2
				1.6X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.16
R1AB_SARS2_4809-4823	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	K DFYD F AVS K GFF KE	5.9X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2

R1AB_SARS2_4845-4859	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	YDYRYNLPMTCDIR	6X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.14
R1AB_SARS2_5273-5287	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	FHLYLQYIRKLHDEL	5X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.13
R1AB_SARS2_5829-5843	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	AWRKAVFISPYNSQN	6.8X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.27
R1AB_SARS2_6073-6087	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	HLIPLMYRGLPWNVV	4X10⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.133
R1AB_SARS2_6153-6167	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	HHSIGFDYVYNPFMI	2.7X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.18
R1AB_SARS2_6681-6695	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	GYAFEHIVYGDFSHS	7.9X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2
R1AB_SARS2_6973-6987	SARS-CoV-2	R (Nsp)	SWNADLYKLMGHFAW	1.3X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.16
SPIKE_SARS2_0133-0147	SARS-CoV-2	S	FQFCNDPFLGVYYHK	8X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.148
SPIKE_SARS2_0265-0279	SARS-CoV-2	S	YYVGYLQPRTFLLKY	7.9X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.214
SPIKE_SARS2_0325-0339	SARS-CoV-2	S	SIVRFPNITNLCPFG	1.6X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.167
				2.7X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.181
SPIKE_SARS2_0553-0567	SARS-CoV-2	S	TESNKKFLPFQQFGR	3.7X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.19
SPIKE_SARS2_0557-0571	SARS-CoV-2	S	KKFLPFQQFGRDIAD	3.2X10⁻³	PED/MILD	0.186
SPIKE_SARS2_0785-0799	SARS-CoV-2	S	VKQIYKTPPIKDFGG	2.7X10⁻³	PED/MILD	0.181
SPIKE_SARS2_1145-1159	SARS-CoV-2	S	LDSFKEELDKYFKNH	3.7X10⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.81
SPIKE_SARS2_1201-1215	SARS-CoV-2	S	QELGKYEQYIKWPWY	9X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.15
SPIKE_SARS2_1205-1219	SARS-CoV-2	S	KYEQYIKWPWYIWLG	3.7X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.19
VME1_SARS2_0005-0019	SARS-CoV-2	M	NGTITVEELKLLLEQ	7.9X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.2
SPIKE_CVHN1_0452_0466	HKU1	S	NFNLSHSHSVYSRYC	1.9X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.171
SPIKE_CVHN1_1144_1158	HKU1	S	GLLFMHFSYKPISEFK	2.3X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.176
				3.2X10 ⁻³	PED/SEVE	0.186
SPIKE_CVHN1_1176_1190	HKU1	S	PKQGYFIKHNDHWMF	1X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.11
SPIKE_CVHN2_0084_0098	HKU1	S	YLSTLWYKPPFLSDF	1.8X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.157
SPIKE_CVHN2_0088_0102	HKU1	S	LWYKPPFLSDFNNGI	3.7X10 ⁻³	PED/MILD	0.19
VME1_CVHN1_0001_0015	HKU1	M	MNKSFLPQFTSDQAV	5X10 ⁻⁴	PED/MILD	0.862
				9X10 ⁻⁴	PED/SEVE	0.848